

ANALYSIS OF BIOGAS GENERATED FROM MAIZE WASTE (COB) AND CARROT LEAVES

A.U SULEIMAN, M.U MUHAMMAD, *M. MUSA, and A.T ARZIKA
Department of Chemistry, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto State.

KEYWORDS; Biogas, Maize waste (cob), Carrot leaves

ABSTRACT

Biogas is an alternative source of fuel which can be generated by decomposition of organic matter such as sheep dung, agricultural waste, maize waste and carrot leaves. This work comparatively analyzes the biogas generated from maize waste (COB) and carrot leaves. Biogas were generated using locally constructed digesters and they were characterized using standard method. The result of the analysis showed that maize cob gave 640cm³ of the gas during the first week of digestion while the carrot leaves gave 900cm³. After the first week, the volume of gas generated continued to decrease. The ash content of the sample was determined and maize cob has 5% while carrot leaves has 20. The concentration of the mineral element showed that the sodium content gave 90ppm and 60ppm for the undigested and digested maize cob respectively, while the concentration of sodium content in the carrot leaves were found to be 1600ppm and 400ppm for both undigested and digested respectively. The concentration of potassium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and nitrogen in all the samples are in appreciable quantities. The analysis showed that (maize cob waste and carrot leaves), can be used to generate biogas and undigested waste can be used as fertilizer

INTRODUCTION

Energy is a fundamental pillar of modern society as well as being an essential building block for socio-economic development, Unido, (2007). The awareness of the imminent depletion of fossil fuels coupled with a global energy crisis has stimulated interest in the research for alternative energy source. (Garba et al, 1996). Biogas production is the decomposition of organic waste materials by means of bacterial action in the absence of oxygen. The biochemical changes that take place in the digester are caused by a mixed culture of bacteria.(Unido 2007)

The biogas produced can provide a clear fuel in the form of gas that has versatile uses. The remnant from the process usually called the spent slurry is compost manure. Beside the fuel and fertilizer, it can provide ameliorated hygienic and sanitary environment and ecological balance (Garba et al, 2003).

Biogas is flammable gas produced by anaerobic fermentation of organic waste materials. Biogas is composed of methane (55-70%), carbon dioxide (30-40%) and a trace of other gases such as nitrogen, hydrogen carbon monoxide, water and hydrogen sulphide (Asere et al, 1992).

Anaerobic decomposition occurs in three stages Hydrolysis, Acidification and Methanogenic in which the intermediate component are converted to methane

Hydrolysis

Wastes of plants and animal material consist mainly of carbohydrates, lipids, proteins and inorganic materials. Large molecular complex substances are solubilized into simpler ones with the help of extra-cellular enzyme released by bacteria, this stage is also known as polymer breakdown stage, for example, the cellulose consisting of polymerized glucose is broken down to dimeric, and then the monomeric sugar molecules (glucose) by cellulolytic bacteria (Malami, 2004).

Acidification

The monomer such as glucose produced in stage one is fermented under anaerobic condition into various acids with the help of enzymes produced by the acid forming bacteria at this stage high molecules are broken down into smaller molecules of less carbon atoms (Acids) which are in a more reduced state than

glucose by acid forming bacteria, the main acids produced in this process are ethanoic acid, propanoic acid, butanoic acid and ethanol (Malami, 2004).

Methanisation

The acids produced in the 2nd stage are processed by methanogenic bacteria to produce methane. The methanogenic bacteria act on the organic acids producing (CH₄) and carbon (iv) oxide (CO₂) in two distinctive routes; one is by reducing CO₂ in the presence of hydrogen produced by other bacterial species as in equation (3) and the other by metabolizing the acetic acid substrate as in equation (4) (Malami, 2004). The biochemical processes above mentioned are expressed by the following equations:

Over important reactions in the production of methane include hydrolysis of carbon (iv) oxide into carbonic acid which is further reduced to methane and water (CH₄, H₂O), hydrolysis of propanoic acid, ethanol. The equation 5,6, & 8 summarize all.

These equation shows that fermentation of these substrates give the same products of methane and carbon dioxide. The organic matter used in the methane fermentation generally contains organic matter and ash. The organic matter is made up of carbohydrates, fats, proteins, tannins, etc.

In the conversion of carbohydrates equal volumes of carbon dioxide and methane are produced. However, not all the CO₂ produced is released, as it is soluble in water. Also CO₂ reacts with (OH) hydroxyl ions to form bio-carbonates.

The concentration of bicarbonate is affected by pH, temperature and pressure, and other materials in the liquid phase. In consequences, the quantity of methane in this stage is increased by conditions that favoured bicarbonates production, primarily, deamination of biodegradable protein in the first and second stages produces hydroxyl ions, when the ammonia released, dissolved in water.

Furthermore, more when animal and human faeces are used, bacteria excreted in the intestine are the main source of sulphur containing protein. In organic sulphur, particularly sulphates can also be bio-chemically converted to H₂S in the fermentation chamber.

Application of Biogas

Biogas can use in the household, community farm or industry for:

1. Heating, cooking and lighting using domestic biogas stoves and lamps.
2. Electricity generation using internal combustion engine, which can be supplied to isolated communities that are away from national grid or the generation power, can be connected to the national grid. It can also be used for irrigation, pumping water, threshing, flouring, feed processing to mention a few.
3. Agricultural production: it is used in crop drying, baking tea, hatching eggs, cultivation of rice seedling and mushrooms, preservation of fruits, grain storage, seed soaking bio-manure e.g. urea and gaseous fertilizers of carbon dioxide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for this research work are maize waste cob and carrot leaves which were all collected within Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto State Nigeria. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Determination of Nitrogen Content

2g of each maize waste and carrot leaves was taken and placed in macro keelhaul flask and one tablet of mercury catalyst was added then 20mls of concentrated H₂SO₄. The sample was then taken for digestion in a fumes cupboard on a digestion block at 400°C for 3hrs; it was then allowed to cool for 24hrs. The sample was then made to a known value of 50mls with distilled water 10mls was then pipetted out of this 50mls into a micro keelhaul flask, 20mls of 40% NaOH was added into the flask and it was then made to 50mls with distilled water, then it was taken to the micro keelhaul distillation and digestion apparatus for distillation. On distillation ammonia gas is produced as the distillate which passes through the condenser and become cooled and drops into a conical flask containing 20mls of boric acid indicator which is dark red in colour until when it changes to green and both samples showed similar change in colour. The conical flask content was titrated against 0.01N H₂SO₄ at end point the colour change observed was from green to pink. % Nitrogen content of the sample can be calculated using.

$$\% \text{ N} = \frac{\text{TV} \times \text{M}(0.001) \times \text{V}(0.0014) \times 50 \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times \text{mls of aliquot}}$$

Determination of Phosphorus

5mls of 20% HCl was added to the ashed sample and the filtered, it was then made up to 50mls. 2mls of the filtrate was taken and 2mls of NH₄Cl to extract the phosphorus content in the sample was added followed by 2mls of NH₄.Mo.O₂₈ which developed colour. The solution was made up to 50ml with distilled water and the absorbance at 660λ with a Jenway 6100 spectrophotometer of both samples was taken separately

which has already been calibrated with standard solution of $\text{NH}_4\text{F} + \text{HCl}$ of 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10ppm the value gotten was used in plotting graph which gives the concentration of phosphorus.

$C \times df \times 25$ $df =$ dilution factor
 $C =$ Conc. Of sample on graph

Determination of Na & K

2mls was taken out of the filtrate from 2.4.8, it was then made up to 50mls with distilled water, it was then taken to flame photometer which has been already calibrated with prepared standard solution of KCl at 0, 2, 6, 8, 10 for determination of potassium and standard solution of NaCl for solution determination was used for the calibration. The results were used in plot in the graph of concentration against absorbance the solution's concentration was used in determination sodium and potassium.

$C \times d.f \times 25$
 $C =$ Concentration of sample on graph
 $Df =$ Dilution factor

Determination of Mg and Ca

- i. 1ml of filtrate from 2.4.8 was diluted with 19mls distilled water to 20mls, 5mls of buffer solution was added followed by 3 drops of KCN, HONH_4HCl , triethanolamine, $\text{K}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, eriochrome black T indicator, which gave blue colour upon titration with 0.01M EDTA the colour change observed was yellowish pink and give total magnesium and calcium present the formula below can be use in calculating it.

$$\frac{\text{TV} \times \text{M} (0.01) \times 100/}{\text{Weight of sample} \times \text{Vol. of aliquot}}$$

- ii. 1ml of sample from 2.4.8 was measured and diluted with 19mls distilled water to 20mls 1ml o f10% NaOH was added followed by 3 drops each of triethanolamine, KCN, HONH_2HCL and a tip of murexide indicator which made the solution purple in colour upon titration with 0.01m EDTA blue colour was observed at end point. Percentage calcium was calculated with formula below:

$$\frac{\text{TV} \times \text{M}(0.01) \times 100}{\text{Weight of Sample} \times \text{Vol. of Sample}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The results of the analysis carried out in chapter two are recorded in Tables below

Table1 Weekly gas production

NO. OF WEEKS	A	B
1	640 cm ³	900 cm ³
2	330 cm ³	550 cm ³
3	300 cm ³	150 cm ³
4		220 cm ³
5	15 cm ³	30 cm ³
6	5 cm ³	100 cm ³
7	30 cm ³	-
8	60 cm ³	-
	1380 cm ³	1950 cm ³

Key: A = Maize waste (cob), B = Carrot leaves.

Table 2 Showing results of Ca, Mg, Na, K, N, P, C/N, and O.C.

NUTRIENTS	SAMPLE	UNDIGESTED	DIGESTED
Na in ppm	A	90	50
	B	1600	400
K in ppm	A	320	1400
	B	13000	225
%Ca	A	0.025	0.055
	B	0.065	0.175
%Mg	A	0.035	0.13
	B	0.095	0.192
P in ppm	A	40	290.6
	B	1125	303.3
% N	A	0.179	0.106
	B	0.567	0.456
C/N	A	190.3	264.5
	B	59.7	54.6
% organic Carbon	A	34.07	27.77
	B	33.84	24.90

Sodium (Na)

The growth of many plants is stimulated by sodium especially in deficiency of potassium; it is a micro element need by plants, which shows essential element for a group of plants exhibiting so-called Hatch-slack path way of carbohydrate metabolism. The result for sodium determination on this work shows that undigested samples of maize waste and carrot leaves with the content of 90ppm and 1600ppm respectively, on the other hand the digested sample has 50ppm and 400ppm respectively showing that the digested sample has lower sodium ion concentration, this could have been due to solubility of sodium compound resulting in having part of the element in effluent water. The sample sludge's can provide required amount to soil because he requirement is small and is in most cases provided by the soil itself. This is in contrast with that of (Uba, 2000)

Potassium (K)

This plays a part in the synthesis of carbohydrates in plant and also assist in the synthesis of protoplasmic protein also increase vigour in plants (Samuel, 1970). The K content of undigested sample were determined to be 3200, 1300ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively, also the concentration in the digested samples were 1400, 225ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively all the sludge sample contains adequate amount of potassium, for soil requirement which is 30ppm.

Magnesium (Mg)

It is also a secondary nutrient required in a small quantity by plants and in most cases can be provide by the soil itself. It plays a vital role in photosynthesis being a constituent of chlorophyll. The magnesium content of the undigested samples is 0.035%, 0.095% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively also that of digested sample gave 0.13%, 0.192% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively. The digested samples show a better result. A kilogram of soil for production requires 0.0274g/kg or 27.4mg/kg of potassium

Calcium (Ca)

The calcium requirement in soil for plant production is low. And the results for undigested sample gave 0.025%, 0.065% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively and the digested samples gave 0.055%, 0.175% for maize plant waste and carrot leaves respectively all are expected to give a better yield when applied to the soil for plant growth having low calcium ion content.

Phosphorus (P)

This is a major plant nutrient which stimulates early root formation, growth, flowering and seed formation. Phosphorus requirement for soil for crop production is 0.0274g p/kg soil, (i.e. 27.4ppm), phosphorus content determined in this work exceed soil requirement the undigested sample gave 40pmm and 1125ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively and the digested sample gave 290.6ppm, 302.3ppm for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively. This means that carrot leaves has higher content because of higher P content in the plant.

Nitrogen (N)

It is a macro nutrient required by plants for growth at all stages. Plant having dark green coloration shows the soil it grew on, nitrogen induce rapid growth, protein content in crops and better yield. The recommended amount of nitrogen per hectare of land is 120kg. The results for nitrogen determination of undigested samples gave 0.179%, 0.56% for maize waste and carrot leaves respectively, and the digested sample gave 0.105%, 0.456%. the carrot leaves has more nitrogen content than the maize waste compared to (Uba, 2000) this can be attributed to moderate nitrogen content in the plant and proper degradation therein. The undigested samples have higher nitrogen content than the digested samples. Which is in support of (Uba, 2000) that it's invariably giving an indication that the anaerobic digestion of the plant material as not good enough due to large amount of nitrogen.

CONCLUSION

The importance of research on biogas cannot be over emphasized considering it is cheap and its availability to the rural populace it also aid the sanitary condition of the rural area. The research carried out showed that both samples produce enough quantity of biogas which can be used to cook, dry crop, irrigate, and pump water. from the analysis, the results obtained in the research work can be concluded as follows.

Beginning of 1st week both samples produced highest yield of biogas, all the samples commence production on the 1st week. the highest daily production of samples B occurred in the first day while sample A 3rd day with 600cm³ and 450cm³ respectively. Biogas can be generated from maize waste and carrot of leaves. The undigested samples are better bio fertilizers than the residue due to their mineral contents. By comparison the gas production by the samples is in this order maize waste > carrot leaves.

REFERENCE

- Aliyu M. (1994). Raw Material and factors affecting biogas production. Paper presented to the Sokoto Energy Research Center for National Training Workshop on Biogas Technology Application. SERC Manual p 111-122
- Aliyu M. Dangoggo S. M and Atiku A. T (199) "Biogas Production from Pigeon Droppings" Nigerian Journal of Renewable Energy Vol. 4 No. 1 Pp 48-52.
- Amamatu D.T.(1995). Physico-Chemical Studies of Biogas Production. A dissertation submitted to UsmanuDanfodiyo University, Sokoto for the award of M. Sc degree pp 4-15 (unpublished).
- Asere A. A. and Aliyu U. O. (1992) "Outlook of Nigeria's Energy Predicament", Nigerian Journal of Renewable Energy Vol. 4 No. 1 pp92-95.
- Eze J. I. (2003) "Some factors affecting biogas production" Nigerian Journal of Solar Energy Vol 4 pp 111-114.
- FAO (1996) A system approach to Biogas Technology. A training manual for extension: (FAO/CMS. 1996).

Garba B. (1994) “Effect of some operating parameters on biogas production rate”. Renewable Energy. An international journal Vol. 6 No. 3 Pp 343

Garba B. (1998). Studies on the chemical composition of biogas and kinetics of its production at varying temperatures. A dissertation submitted to UsmanDanfodiyo University Sokoto. The award of PhD degree.Pp 1-250 (unpublished)

Garba B. Zuru A. A. and Sambo, A. S. (1996) “Effect of Slurry Concentration of Biogas Production from cattle dung”. Nigerian Journal of renewable energy Vol. 4, No. 2, Pp. 38-43

Garba B. Zuru A. A. Sambo A. S. and B/Yauri U. A. (2003) “Kinetic study of methane and Biogas production from cow dung. Nigerian Journal of Solar Energy Vol. 4 Pp. 100-110.

Kangmin L. (1997) Integration of Aquaculture into macro agriculture. A paper presented at the UNDP/UNU integrated biogas system workshop Suva. Fiji, May 5-9, 1997.

Limcanglo-Lopez, P. D. (1989). The use of shrubs and green fodder by non-ruminants shrubs and tree fodder for farm animals, proceedings for workshop in Denpasar Pp 24-29 Indonesia.

Machido D. A. Zuru A. A. and Akpan E. E. (1996).Effect of some inorganic nutrients and the performance of cow dung as a substitute of biogas production, Nigerian Journal of renewable energy Vol. 4 No. 2 Pp 34-37